

THE ROLE OF IDEA EXPRESSION IN THE FORMATION OF ARTISTIC CRITERIA IN THE WORK OF OYDINNISO AND GULJAMOL ASKAROVA

Akmuratova Bibisanem
Karakalpak State University
named after Berdak

***Abstract.** In the article, the synthesis of artistic attitude and semantic essence was interpreted in the poetry of Aydinniso and Guljamol Askarova. The poetic image is an extremely vivid and meaningful artistic device, and it is an aesthetic center that embodies the ideological and spiritual power of the poem.*

***Key words:** modern, metaphor, rhythm, art, expression.*

Oydinniso and G.Askarova are considered to be one of the leading representatives of modern Uzbek poetry. In their work, the conflict of feeling and consciousness turns into a sign that determines the uniqueness of the psyche of the image. The main weapon of literature is the word. Indeed, a literary work is not only a means of information. Wisdom, enlightenment, education, traditional moral culture and philosophy of life are synthesized in it. As the art of words transforms the image object into its own system of images, while artistically researching reality and the fate of people, it re-polishes them from the point of view of the laws of beauty. Original art can give such a meaning to simple and everyday objects that, as a result, the depicted content acquires a historical meaning. The artist conveys his perceived reality, the world, his thoughts and ideas to others through words. The appropriate use of phrases is necessary and necessary, especially for poetry. As you delve deeper into the poetic world created by the power of the poet's words, you will believe in its perfection, maturity in form, and completeness in content.

In almost all of the poet's poems, the scope of the subject and the characteristics of expression are consistent with their uniqueness, and they show the most effective forms of expression. Although the scope of the poetess's research appeared in the form of various trends, colors and even, in a certain sense, mutually exclusive tendencies, none of them left a trace. By mixing and complementing each other, a qualitatively new poetic style was created. If we take into account that the consciousness of the creator is determined by the consistency of words, sound, and tone, it becomes easier to achieve the intended goal. By identifying the poetic elements formed on the basis of word and function, in revealing the essence of the artistic text, it is possible to observe the equality of expression and image, the combination of analysis and interpretation, the integrity of imagination, form and content, the compatibility of signs and tools, the cohesion of worldview and skills:

If we pay attention to poetess Guljamol Askarova's poetry:

Oh, they say, wow other countries,
Friends traveling together.
They say I'm weird
The verb has many diminutives
In the interpretation of the poet Oydinnisa:
Sometimes I sang like the wind,
Sometimes I poured like rain.
Turn into four seasons,
I read as you, as you.

In the logically complete thoughts of both creators, one common feature is clearly visible before our eyes: in the wonder of the poet, the strange image of great and pure love, like the light of the sun growing from a particle, rings like silver in allusions in its own way. They share a happy mood with a transparent drop. We paid serious attention to the objective and subjective aspects of both artists. Like the ancient minarets of Samarkand, in the eyes of the poets who love the Motherland, which expresses the breath of today in a new way, in the form of their poems, the Motherland is one, the Motherland is one.

Depicting the image of the Motherland in one's own work is the primary characteristic of a true artist. Although everyone has their own worldview, living conditions, aspirations, and goals, sincerely loving and honoring the Motherland in the huge fortress called the heart forms true patriotism and cherishes it.

We witness the creation of the following interpretations by poetess Guljamol Askarova in her poem "Vatan" with her brave, martial and rhythmic musicality:

Maybe in a foreign country
We are likely to be surprised.
My home is good for me.
Open and close the door every day.

The artistic components of the poem: in the essence of allegory and imagery, the fact that love for the Motherland is found in objects that are simply unimaginable becomes more alive. Especially the poetess loves her country

knowing every corner as sacred, he can't stop his excitement even for a moment. This surprise and excitement can be understood as the highest value for him - seeing the Motherland at a higher level. On the one hand, glorification of Vtan lies at the root of ordinary life and philosophical observations, and on the other hand, the poetess compares her own love freely and in the manner of opening and closing the

door. This simile fully confirms the originality of depicting the Motherland from other artists.

The well-known poet Bahrom Rozimuhammad, who wrote the lyrics to her book "Hovur", said that we consider Aydinnisa to be a full-fledged "modern" poetess. there are many. Modern allusions in Ammoun make the reader think. While organizing Oydinnisa's book of poetry called "Draft", we find more traditional "interpretations" in it, which are slightly different from the modern style. The lyrics of Oydinniso and Guljamol Askarova are unique in that they strive to raise the quality of advanced Uzbek artistic traditions.

In general, in the interpretations of both creators, it is evident that they analyzed the theme of the Motherland in their own way. Because in his figurative allusions and interpretations, he is full of wonder and excitement. After all, the task of a literary critic is not to know the existing interpretations, but to interpret and evaluate the work based on them (sometimes agreeing with them, sometimes denying them) from the point of view of today.

In the words of Professor N. Karimov, << A poem is an organism in itself, and a word is its cell. Just as every cell of an organism needs to be healthy and breathing in order to be alive, so every word needs to give its blood to the image that is the heart of the poem and make it move. >>. It is worth noting that the word poetic, which is selected, sorted and used based on the essence of artistic thought, brightens the thought. It can be based on a bright poetic word. So, a poetic image is created by a layer of artistic words with a symbolic meaning and ways of creating different meanings of the word, in other words, in the process of the activity of the poetic word in the field of artistic observation. The emergence of poetic words that are the basis of artistic images and their entry into poetic form is a product of a certain life process.

The poetic image is an extremely vivid and meaningful artistic device, and it is an aesthetic center that embodies the ideological and spiritual power of the poem. The artistic thought that the poet wants to express, the magic of the words he uses, is hidden in this poetic image. Because the poetic <<brightness, originality, originality of the image depends on the depth of the poet's worldview, the perfect formation of the aesthetic ideal>>. As a product of the individuality of this poetic skill, in R. Musurman's poetry, trees, flowers, soil, mountains, wind, snow, fog, clouds, bees, sparrows, ants, grass, leaves, fire, light, stars, sun, moon , the system of poetic images such as road, hazon, nihol, winter, autumn, summer and winter is key to the poetic evaluation of reality:

The tree, our time,

Our sky is the same, why?
Your hands are so generous
I am ashamed to look at my hand...

The poet assigns a social task to the image of a tree. It is a disturbing pain and suffering about the social consequences of selfishness, which is wrapped around the hearts of people. As a result of adding socio-philosophical content to the image of a tree, its semantic image is clarified, that is, nuances of meaning - symbolic interpretations appear. During the development of our lyrics, the tree became a means of artistic interpretation of human nature, a factor of studying and understanding his thoughts. << After the trees, which are an element of nature, moved to poetry and art, it is noteworthy that they reflect the specific psychological state of the lyrical hero, the ideals, interests and aspirations of the people of this or that era>>. Poetic image is the main element of the artistic device of a poetic work. Poetic images of nature's life appear on the basis of giving a significant social background to the views of the beauty of the creative world. Each poetic image is a natural drawing of reality.

He got rich like a bud,
A knot in my bosom.

In the poet's landscape lyrics, in her literary interpretation of human nature and the spirit of society, observation is evident. Lessons of thought directed to folk wisdom appear, absorbing the meaning of life lessons. In particular, take a look at all the actions of humanity. Both good and bad are governed by the man within. It has a strong influence of Eastern poetics. In particular, didactic content forms its basis, while life lessons and lessons learned from living are expressed more in the form of recognition. "Duals" are the poet's long-term expectations, conversations with people, the meanings he heard when he saw and heard, the confessions that leaked from the layers of his soul. They carry an impressive and instructive idea because they are built on the ground of life.

Referens:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity. -Uzbekistan. 2017.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. - Tashkent.: Uzbekistan, 2018.
3. Literary theory. - Tashkent: Science, 1978.
4. Obviously. Draft. - Tashkent: Literature and Art, 2016.
5. Kazakboy Yoldosh. Open word. - Tashkent: Tafakkur, 2019.
6. <http://ww.ziyouz.com/>.